

Phantom Channel Defense Against Coordinated Sensor Spoofing in Autonomous Vehicles

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Abstract—Modern Autonomous Vehicle (AV) perception architecture relies on multi-sensor fusion models that combine views from various sensors for a more robust perception stack. The architectural strength rests on the assumption that the sensor inputs are trustworthy. However, recent studies demonstrated coordinated cross-modal attacks that can simultaneously manipulate various sensors with physically consistent false detections, a critical vulnerability. The current fallback strategies for such sensor conflict situations are Minimal Risk Condition (MRC) hard stops, Level 2 degradation, or manual driving handover, all of which could disrupt continuous operation and themselves become a denial of service if continuously triggered.

This document proposes a Phantom Channel Defense System, an isolated software-defined subsystem that operates alongside the primary autonomous driving stack. The system introduces an independently trusted sensing channel based on frequency-agile radar and employs cryptographic mechanisms to maintain integrity even under a white-box threat model in which the attacker is assumed to have knowledge of the vehicle’s hardware, software and phantom system.

Upon detection of a conflict among perception sensors, the proposed Phantom Channel Defense System activates an isolated fallback subsystem that independently validates the vehicle’s environment using frequency-agile radar operating outside the primary perception stack. By leveraging cryptographically derived challenge-response mechanisms and an independently trusted sensing channel, the system enables resilient autonomous operation even when the primary multi-sensor fusion system is suspected to be compromised. A controlled hand-back mechanism is further incorporated to mitigate repeated attack and denial-of-service conditions.

Index Terms—Autonomous vehicles, sensor spoofing, multi-sensor fusion, cross-modal attack, frequency-agile radar, HMAC authentication, key derivation, fallback navigation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous Vehicles that operate at SAE Level 4 [1] and above rely on the perception stack in the system to interpret the environment and drive without needing human intervention. Modern stacks use multi-sensor fusion models combining inputs from various sensors like Camera, LiDAR, radar to build a unified representation of the environment that can help the planning and control layer to navigate the vehicle which are more robust than relying on single-sensor systems. BEVFusion [2] is one such model that has become a widely adopted architecture for this class of system that projects the sensor features into a shared Bird’s-Eye view coordinate space fused by a learned network, producing high-confidence 3D detections that drive vehicle navigation.

Prior research has studied numerous attacks and defenses against single-modality sensor spoofing targeting LiDAR and camera systems. These defenses range from physical-layer signal authentication techniques [3] [4] to machine-learning [5] or deep-learning based [6] anomaly detection frameworks, as well as occlusion-based detection [7]. While effective against attacks on individual sensors, such approaches were developed in the context of single-modality perception systems. With the introduction of multi-sensor fusion architectures, the threat landscape for autonomous vehicle perception systems changed. By combining observations from multiple sensors into a unified representation, MSF models can perform cross-validation between the sensor inputs and may therefore have increased resilience against attacks that target single sensing modality. For example, an attack that alters the output of a camera-based perception pipeline may create inconsistencies with observations of LiDAR, radar, HD maps or other sources during fusion.

However, the robustness provided by multi-sensor fusion architecture depends on the assumption that at least one sensing modality remains trustworthy. A motivated attacker capable of manipulating multiple sensors simultaneously may be able to introduce physically consistent false observations that fool the fusion process and are interpreted as legitimate objects. This limitation is demonstrated by the Cross-Modal Phantom attack [8], which coordinates camera and LiDAR spoofing to inject consistent false features into the shared perception pipeline. Since the manipulated observations appear consistent across sensing modalities with high confidence, the multi-sensor fusion defenses and consistency checks may be insufficient to identify the attack. Existing fallback mechanisms in such situations typically rely on strategies such as Minimal Risk Condition (MRC) stopping, degraded operating modes, or driver handover [1]. While these approaches prioritize safety, they may interrupt autonomous operation which itself can be denial-of-service if triggered repeatedly.

With the emergence of coordinated cross-modal attacks, a fundamental architectural gap is exposed in the current perception systems. The absence of an independently verifiable sensing channel whose trustworthiness is not dependent on the primary perception pipeline. As demonstrated by the Cross-Modal Phantom [8] attack discussed previously, adversarial influence can fool multiple sensing modalities and compromise the integrity of the fused environmental representation, making it difficult to establish trust in perception outputs as the fusion

process is compromised. Prior work has also explored auxiliary, tamper-resistant sensors [9] that activate during sensor conflict conditions to provide additional source of environment information. However, such approaches continue to observe the same external environment as the primary perception system and therefore remain subject to same physical scene presented to the vehicle. Therefore, fallback mechanisms that rely on sensor data originating from known and predictable sensing principles may remain vulnerable to sufficiently capable attacker under a white-box threat model. These limitations motivate the need for an independently trusted sensing system whose operational characteristics cannot be fully anticipated during system operation.

To address this challenge, this paper presents the Phantom Channel Defense, a security architecture that introduces an isolated and independently trusted sensing domain capable of validating environmental observations independently outside the primary perception stack. When conflicts arise within the main perception system, the proposed architecture enables continued operation through an isolated fallback mechanism rather than relying exclusively on emergency stops or human intervention. The remainder of this paper describes the related work, system design, evaluation plan, limitations and future work of the proposed architecture and conclusion.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Single-Modality Sensor Spoofing: Attacks and Defenses

Early research in AV sensor security focused on attacks against individual sensing modalities, primarily LiDAR and camera, evaluated against perception pipelines that did not assume multi-sensor fusion and cross-validation yet. Sun et al. [7] demonstrated in their work that LiDAR-based perception is vulnerable to black-box based spoofing attacks that exploits ignored occlusion patterns in the LiDAR point clouds. A real object physically blocks returning laser ray behind it, producing an occlusion shadow which an injected fake object doesn't have. Their defense, CARLO, treats this shadow as an invariant physical feature, reducing attack success rate from approximately 80% to 5.5%.

Nassi et al. [5] identified a vulnerability in the camera-based ADAS, demonstrating that commercial systems including the Tesla Model X and Mobileye 630 react to depthless objects displayed just for milliseconds via digital billboards or projectors. Their countermeasure, GhostBusters, use a committee of lightweight CNNs assessing light, context, surface and depth properties from camera data. Lin et al. [6] extended in this line of work and came up with PhaDe, generalizing detection across previously unseen attack device sources using a multi-head self-attention fusion deep-learning model over artificially constructed image modalities.

Another variation of work moves below the perception layer. Hu et al. [4] proposed verifying LiDAR return signals using the Doppler frequency shift. They argued that perception-layer defenses can be evaded by a motivated attacker who fabricates points to satisfy the contextual relationships in the environment. Whereas Doppler characteristics of legitimate

and spoofed signals are fundamentally different at the physical layer. Suzuki et al. [3] presents a similar study with FFT-based analysis of raw time-of-flight data demonstrating that infrared emission tracking of the victim LiDAR can be used for spoofing attacks that can be practically achievable against moving vehicles at highway speed. This study establishes that the threat addressed is real-world feasible and not just a theoretical assumption. Both these defenses are more robust than perception-layer approaches as they operate on the physical layer before the point cloud is formed making such an attack harder to evade like using fake point crafting. However, both the ideas share a practical limitation. They require access to raw LiDAR signal data that the current commercially produced LiDAR do not expose and only output the finished point cloud. For these ideas to be practically implemented, it would require firmware modification or purpose-built hardware, leaving them as research proposals rather than deployable solutions on existing AV platforms.

It is to be noted that none of the attacks or defenses described till now in this section, were developed in the context of, or evaluated against multi-sensor fusion architectures to our knowledge. Each assumes a perception pipeline relying primarily on one sensing modality and each defense is designed to protect or authenticate that modality. This is not a limitation of the works individually but rather a reflection of the threat landscape at the time. Multi-sensor fusion was not yet the dominant production architecture. With the widespread adoption of MSF architectures, the threat model and landscape changed fundamentally.

B. Multi-Sensor Fusion and the Cross-Modal Phantom Attack

The shift towards Multi-Sensor Fusion architectures introduced additional resilience against the class of single-modality attacks described in Section A. By requiring cross-modal consistency across various sensors in the system in a shared representation, MSF architectures introduced a structural property that single-sensor defenses do not possess. An attack confined to one modality produced detectable disagreement with the other sensors during fusion. A fake LiDAR injection with no corresponding camera or radar return, or a camera detection with no LiDAR geometry behind it would show up as a sensor confidence asymmetry that a properly fused system would flag suspicious. In this sense, the fusion process introduces an additional layer of validation that may increase resilience against the attacks discussed previously, not because they were weak but because the fusion architecture's cross-modal consistency requirement is itself a structural defense against single-modality manipulation.

However, this robustness depends on a foundational assumption that at least more than half the sensors are trustworthy and provides honest cross-check. But Khan and Hasan [8] showed that a motivated attacker can invalidate this assumption. The Cross-Modal Phantom attack coordinates an infrared laser projection device and an electromagnetic interference injection device to place consistent false features into both camera and LiDAR streams at the same spatial location in PointPillars rep-

resentation. Because both the modalities now agree, the fusion model's cross-modal consistency requirement is satisfied by the attack and the system reports a high confidence detection of a phantom obstacle. This defeats the base property of consistency requirement in these models that would otherwise flag single-modality attacks. This is a qualitative shift in the threat landscape. The Cross-Modal Phantom attacks is not simply another sensor attack, but one that is specifically engineered to defeat the structural property that made MSF architectures more robust than everything that preceded them.

C. Fallback, Degradation, and Auxiliary Sensing Strategies

While multi-sensor fusion models can successfully flag discrepancies between sensor modalities, the next plausible question would be how they handle such a situation. SAE J3016 [1] formally defines the Dynamic Driving Task Fallback and the Minimal Risk Condition (MRC) as the standard response when an ADS encounters a conflicted situation, is a stable stopped condition such as pulling onto the shoulder, or in reduce to lower automation levels and handover to a human driver. While MRC and driver handover are appropriate responses to genuine system failures, an attacker who can repeatedly trigger a perceived conflict can repeatedly force the vehicle into MRC or degraded operation, effectively achieving denial-of-service condition against an otherwise functional vehicle.

Soryal [9] proposed an architecture to sensor conflict that avoids immediate MRC. An auxiliary tamper-resistant sensor, housed in shielding resistant to wireless electronic signals and concealed within the vehicle body which activates on conflict detection is used to cross-validate the primary sensor suite. This work is the closest prior architectural precedent to the approach taken in the design presented in this document, presenting a conflict-triggered activation of an independent sensing channel to avoid relying on MRC alone. Taking inspiration from this, we identified its central limitation as the motivation for our own design. Since the auxiliary sensor observes the same physical environment as the primary sensors through a conventional sensing principle, it remains subject to the same scene manipulation that triggered the original conflict. It cannot distinguish a real obstacle from a coordinated cross-modal phantom, since both present identically to any conventional sensor placed in the same environment. The auxiliary sensing approach addresses hardware-level tampering but not environmental manipulation, and therefore does not resolve the threat introduced by scene manipulation as in [8].

The proposed design in this document provides a sensing channel whose trustworthiness is independent of what the vehicle's main perception sensors observe in the environment which is the central architectural gap that motivates the Phantom Channel Defense. Any sensing mechanism whose operational characteristics are fixed and fully known to the attacker may be susceptible to manipulation under a white-box threat model. This assumption is realistic in the automotive domain, since commercially available vehicles can be acquired and studied by adversaries, as demonstrated by Miller

and Valasek's seminal automotive security research [10]. The infrared laser and IEMI devices in Cross-Modal Phantom [8] work precisely because the attacker knows exactly the physical signatures the camera and LiDAR expect to see, and can engineer inputs that produce those signatures. An auxiliary sensor of any conventional type, camera or LiDAR or radar, operating at known frequency are subject to the same logic. Given sufficient knowledge and capability, the attacker can prepare a manipulation that satisfies the physical principle the sensor relies on and use it to fool the system. One way to counter it is to introduce a sensing parameter that changes unpredictably at the moment of challenge such that the attacker cannot anticipate even with full architectural knowledge of the system. Rather than adding another sensor that sees the same world through a predictable principle, the Phantom Channel Defense introduces a sensing channel whose operational characteristics are cryptographically derived at runtime from a secret unavailable to the attacker, such that the attacker cannot know what the channel is looking for until after the challenge has already been issued.

D. Foundations for the Phantom Channel

The Phantom Channel Defense's security rests on the premise that the attacker cannot predict the phantom radar's operating parameters, even under a white-box threat model. This requires (i) a source of entropy unknown and unpredictable by the attacker, (ii) A mechanism to derive shared secrets from that entropy without transmitting them in the clear and (iii) a mechanism to authenticate challenge-response exchanges using those secrets.

For (i), NIST SP 800-90B [11] formally defines the requirements for physical entropy sources used in random bit generation, establishing basis for treating ambient acoustic noise as a valid entropy source rather than an ad hoc design choice. For (ii), HKDF [12] provides the standard construction for deriving multiple independent cryptographic keys from a single entropy source which here is used to derive both the session key K and the frequency sequence FS from the same acoustic seed without correlating them. Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman [13] is used for the key exchange. It was chosen over classical Diffie-Hellman for its lower computational and bandwidth overhead since it would be a relevant consideration as the embedded radar controller has constrained computation power. For (iii), HMAC [14] provides the authentication primitive for the challenge-response protocol between the phantom system and the radar controller, ensuring that a response cannot be accepted unless it was produced by an entity in possession of K .

Lastly, ISO/SAE 21434 [15] and ISO 26262 [16] motivate the two-container isolation architecture. ISO/SAE 21434 frames component segregation as a cybersecurity control such that compromise of one component should not trivially pivot to compromise another. ISO 26262 Part 6 imposes freedom-from-interference requirements between software components for safety reasons. The Phantom Channel Defense's main system and the phantom system separation is an instance

of an isolation already mandated in production AV software architectures for both reasons and applied here to ensure phantom systems cryptographic material and operational state remain unreachable even if main system is fully compromised.

E. Radar-Only Navigation as Fallback

The choice of frequency-agile FMCW radar as the phantom sensor was made instead of something like dynamically tunable LiDAR as they are already commercially deployed in automotive applications [17], whereas dynamic wavelength LiDAR remains a research-stage capability. It was important as this hardware choice in turn constrains the fallback navigation module to radar-only operation. Herraes et al. [18] demonstrated radar-only odometry and mapping for automotive scenarios using Doppler velocity measurements for ego-motion estimation even when the sensor’s field of view is partially obstructed which is directly applicable to the reduced-speed safe-hold operation of phantom system. Overbye and Saripalli [19] demonstrated radar-only local navigation for ground-plane estimation and obstacle avoidance over extended paths, with accuracy comparable to LiDAR-based methods at low speed. Together, these establish that radar-only navigation is a validated capability rather than a novel and unproven component of the proposed architecture and the fallback module reliance on radar alone is a demonstrated choice rather than a compromised safety fallback.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

The Phantom Channel Defense introduces the Phantom System as an additional isolated container alongside the Main System’s existing multi-container stack, communicating through a minimal two-signal interface and system state information exchange, a `/conflict_flag` from the Main System to the Phantom System on conflict detection, and a `/handback_ready` from the Phantom System to the Main System on confirmation that the Main System is ready to take over the cruise control (Figure 1) and the Main System state for Handback Conditions check. This isolation satisfies both ISO 26262 [16] freedom-from-interference requirements and ISO/SAE 21434 [15] component segregation requirements. The hardware additions beyond the standard AV stack are a frequency-agile FMCW radar unit and one MEMS microphone. The Main System’s LiDAR, camera and radar are entirely undisturbed.

A. Main System

The Main System includes a full Multi-Sensor Fusion based AV stack across different functional layers (Figure 2).

The sensor and odometry subsystem comprises camera, LiDAR, radar, GPS/GNSS and IMU. An Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) fuses GPS and IMU into a continuous pose estimate that feeds the MSF model, localization, command generation and conflict detector as an independent side channel that does not pass through the perception model.

The MSF model processes camera frames through a ResNet CNN backbone and LiDAR point clouds through a 3D sparse

Fig. 1. **Phantom Channel Defense — System Overview:** The Main System and Phantom System run as isolated containers, communicating via `/conflict_flag` and `/handback_ready`

Fig. 2. **Main System — Functional Layer Architecture:** Sensor-to-actuator pipeline of the Main System, from perception through planning to the conflict detector and safety guardrail

CNN, projecting both into a shared representation aligned to world coordinates using EKF odometry. Radar Doppler velocity data enter the shared representation at radar target locations. Camera and LiDAR feature maps are fused by a learned network, producing per-sensor confidence scores and Detection 3D Array output. This sensors-and-odometry layer, together with the MSF fusion stage, is where the Cross Modal Phantom [8] attack is operated, placing consistent false features into the same environmental location through coordinated IR laser and IEMI injection.

Object Tracking runs the Kalman filter prediction, Hungarian algorithm matching, ID assignment, track management and trajectory smoothing, producing a Tracked Object Array with unique IDs, class, position, velocity history and frame age. Localization matches detected static objects against the HD map, refining ego pose to centimeter-level accuracy and extracting a local lane graph. Scene Understanding, Trajectory Prediction, Behavior Planning and Motion Planning then produce a Planned Trajectory that Command Generation converts into Proposed Actuator Commands forwarded to the Conflict Detector.

The Conflict Detector checks three conditions in parallel on every cycle (Figure 3). Condition A checks whether the deviation between the proposed actuator commands and the EKF dead-reckoning predicted trajectory exceeds certain threshold. A genuine obstacle produces deviation consistent with gradual detection history, while an injected phantom appearing for the first time produces an immediate large deviation with no dead-reckoning basis. Condition B checks the frame age of the object driving the unusual command. Real objects accumulate track history across frames, injected phantom objects fail the recency threshold. Condition C checks asymmetry across per-sensor confidence scores. A phantom object injected via IR laser and IEMI achieves high camera and LiDAR confidence but low radar confidence and thereby large difference between per-sensor confidence scores. While radar disagreement contributes to conflict detection, the architecture does not assume that any conventional sensor will remain uncompromised under all attack scenarios. By targeting a majority of the sensor modalities (more than half), the attacker exploits the fusion architecture’s unifying logic, allowing the high confidence scores of the compromised sensors to override the low confidence of the uncompromised sensors and force a fraudulent object detection. Even if the unified confidence is high, there would be a large gap between the per-sensor confidence scores. All three conditions must satisfy simultaneously to raise a CONFLICT flag, minimizing false positives from genuine sensor detections. On conflict, `/conflict_flag` is published along with last clean guardrail-approved command to the Phantom System and the Main System’s planning output is suspended from actuators until it receives `/handback_ready` flag back from the Phantom System. The Main System continues running internally, providing data for handback recovery conditions.

The Safety Guardrail sits between command output and actuators for both normal and fallback operation, applying

Fig. 3. **Conflict Detector — Three-Condition AND Logic:** Conditions A, B, and C are checked in parallel; all three must fire simultaneously to raise the CONFLICT flag

jerk, steering rate, and brake deceleration limits. Both systems have to go through this layer for their commands to reach the actuators.

B. Phantom System

The Phantom System (Figure 4) implements a cryptographic challenge protocol and radar-only navigation as an additional container alongside the Main System stack. It remains completely silent during normal operation and holds no runtime role until activated by `/conflict_flag` after a start up protocol (Figure 5).

The phantom sensor used is a frequency-agile FMCW radar unit entirely separate from the Main System’s radar. Changing the operating frequency changes the beam direction, range resolution and detection cone geometry. An attacker who cannot predict the current frequency cannot pre-tune jamming, cannot know beam direction and cannot inject returns satisfying the expected physical constraints for that frequency profile. Frequency-agile FMCW radar is commercially produced at scale in the automotive sector [17] making this a near-production hardware assumption. Dynamic wavelength LiDAR was evaluated as an alternative for the same architectural reason but it is still a research stage capability and unavailable in commercial production. This hardware choice in turn influences the fallback navigation to radar-only operation, supported by validated prior work [18] [19].

The startup protocol executes once per journey before the vehicle moves (Figure 5). One hundred milliseconds of ambient audio is recorded from the MEMS microphone. SHA3-256 is computed over the raw audio bytes to produce a 256-bit seed S, formally grounded as a valid physical entropy

Fig. 4. **Phantom System — Internal Architecture:** Flow from startup through conflict activation, HMAC challenge, radar-only fallback, and handback

source under NIST SP 800-90B [11]. Session key K is derived from S via HKDF-SHA256 [15] and exchanged with the radar controller via Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman [13], chosen for its computational efficiency on an embedded radar controller. The frequency sequence FS , W and M is derived from S via a separate HKDF invocation respectively and stored in Phantom System. After startup, only K exist in the Phantom System memory and radar controller firmware and the rest i.e. FS , W and M in the Phantom System and it goes silent.

Fig. 5. **Phantom System — Startup Protocol and Key Derivation:** Acoustic entropy is sampled, hashed, and processed via HKDF to derive session key K , frequency sequence FS , W and M and exchange K with controller via ECDH.

On receiving `/conflict_flag`, the Phantom System simultaneously freezes the last clean command, ramps vehicle speed to 60%-80% via jerk-limited deceleration, and begins the multi-round HMAC challenge protocol. The safe-hold speed reduction eliminates the MRC hard stop and its denial-of-service vulnerability. The vehicle continues moving at reduced speed, preventing an attacker from repeatedly forcing a stationary recovery state. The frequency sequence

position never resets, ensuring that successive conflicts use new frequency values.

Each challenge round selects the next frequency profile from the FS, builds and signs an instruction with HMAC-SHA3-256 [14] using K , sends it to the radar controller, verifies the response HMAC, and applies physics-validity checks to the radar return. If any round fails, the radar scan for that round has not been authenticated, and the Phantom System does not yet treat it as ground truth. Instead, it navigates provisionally on this unauthenticated data for a randomly derived M seconds before retrying the challenge from the next FS position. This provisional navigation is a temporary, lower-trust holding state distinct from the authenticated radar-only fallback navigation, since the radar's authenticity has not yet been cryptographically confirmed for the current cycle. The random window prevents an attacker from timing a jamming pause to match a fixed retry interval. If all N rounds pass, the phantom radar scan is trusted as ground truth and the Phantom System operates exclusively on authenticated phantom radar data and starts the Handback Conditions check.

Handback from the Phantom System to the Main System requires three conditions to hold simultaneously for a sustained window of W seconds derived from K (Figure 6). Condition 1 requires the Main System's proposed command to remain within the threshold of EKF dead-reckoning, the triggering detection resolved and all three main sensors mutually consistent. Condition 2 requires the phantom radar's authenticated view to be consistent with what the Main System is claiming. Condition 3 requires both the previous conditions to hold continuously for the full W -second window. The random W prevents an attacker from calculating how long to pause their attack to force handback. If the radar-only navigation module finds no drivable space, the Phantom System triggers a controlled progressive deceleration to zero with hazard lights which is a more deliberate physics-aware stop and not an MRC panic stop.

Fig. 6. **Phantom System — Three-Condition Handback Protocol:** Handback requires Conditions 1 and 2 to hold continuously for a sustained window of W seconds (Condition 3) before control returns to the Main System.

C. Attacker Scenario

The attacker scenario (Figure 7) operates under a white-box model. The adversary has full knowledge of the system architecture including the existence of the Phantom System, the radar sensor location, the frequency-agile radar and the cryptographic algorithms employed. What the attacker wouldn't know is K, FS, W or M which are all derived from acoustic entropy at startup.

The attacker deploys an IR laser device to project adversarial patterns into the camera's field of view, an IEMI injection device to produce synthetic LiDAR point clusters at the same 3D location with both manipulations coordinated to satisfy the MSF cross-modal consistency requirement across more than half of the sensing modalities (here, 2 out of 3). This produces high-confidence phantom detection and triggers an emergency braking or evasive steering command. Without the Phantom System it reaches the actuators. With the Phantom System the unusual command triggers the conflict conditions. For Condition A, the sudden phantom object can produce large deviation from the expected actuator commands. For Condition B, the fake object appears suddenly as the fake points are inserted which gives them a shorter frame age compared to gradually approaching objects. For Condition C, the Main System's radar reports normal or lesser confidence while camera and LiDAR produce significantly higher confidence, producing asymmetry in the condition. It is worth noting that the Main System's radar itself is not targeted in this scenario and could in principle have served as the disambiguating signal. However, the architecture cannot rely on any single conventional sensor remaining trustworthy by assumption, since a white-box attacker capable of compromising camera and LiDAR simultaneously could just as easily redirect their attack toward a different sensor combination, leaving a different subset of sensors uncompromised each time. The Phantom System is therefore not the Main System's radar repurposed for verification, but a separate, cryptographically authenticated channel whose trustworthiness does not depend on guessing which conventional sensor the attacker chose to leave alone. The Phantom System activates and challenges the environment using its own frequency-agile radar at a frequency the attacker cannot predict, entirely independent of the Main System's radar. The phantom radar returns a clean scan showing no obstacle at the claimed location and the vehicle navigates safely under radar-only fallback on a sensor the attacker never targeted and cannot reach.

IV. EVALUATION PLAN

As this work presents a security architecture design rather than an implemented system, no experimental results are reported. Instead, this section outlines the proposed evaluation methodology that would be used to validate the Phantom Channel Defense following its implementation.

The first stage of evaluation would focus on functional validation of the architecture. A simulation environment incorporating a Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) perception stack and autonomous driving pipeline would be used to verify

Fig. 7. **Attacker Scenario — Cross-Modal Phantom Attack and Defense Response:** Coordinated IR and IEMI injection triggers the conflict detector; the Phantom System authenticates the environment and navigates safely under radar-only fallback.

correct operation of the proposed workflow. Test scenarios would confirm proper activation of the Conflict Detector, successful transition from the Main System to the Phantom System, execution of the cryptographic challenge-response protocol, operation of radar-only fallback navigation [18] [19], and eventual handback to the Main System once recovery conditions are satisfied.

A second stage of evaluation would focus on threshold tuning and detection accuracy. The proposed Conflict Detector relies on trajectory deviation thresholds, object recency thresholds, and confidence-score asymmetry thresholds. These parameters would require empirical tuning to balance false positive and false negative rates. Evaluation scenarios would include normal driving conditions, sensor noise, temporary localization errors, sudden obstacle appearances, and other benign events that could potentially trigger unnecessary fallback activation. The objective would be to identify threshold values that minimize unintended activations while maintaining sensitivity to genuine perception anomalies.

Security-focused evaluation would assess the effectiveness

of the architecture against a range of perception attacks. These scenarios would include single-modality spoofing attacks against camera or LiDAR systems, coordinated cross-modal attacks similar to the Cross-Modal Phantom attack [8], replay attacks against the challenge protocol, and attempts to interfere with the frequency-agile radar subsystem. Metrics such as attack detection rate, successful attack rate, fallback activation frequency, challenge-response success rate, and average recovery time would be recorded to characterize system behavior under adversarial conditions.

Finally, the architecture would be assessed against relevant safety and cybersecurity standards. This assessment would examine whether the proposed isolation mechanisms satisfy ISO 26262 [16] freedom-from-interference principles and whether the separation of the Phantom System aligns with cybersecurity architecture recommendations defined by ISO/SAE 21434 [15]. While such an assessment would not constitute formal certification, it would provide an indication of the architecture's suitability for deployment within safety-critical autonomous vehicle systems.

V. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

The security of the proposed Phantom Channel Defense ultimately depends on the unpredictability of the acoustic entropy [11] seed generated during system startup. In the current design, the salting mechanism used alongside the acoustic entropy source is intentionally simplified and should be considered a placeholder rather than a finalized cryptographic component. An attacker capable of approximating vehicle startup conditions may attempt to influence the acoustic environment, for example by generating sustained uniform audio intended to reduce the entropy of captured microphone samples. Future work should investigate stronger salting mechanisms based on independent hardware-derived entropy sources such as ring oscillator jitter, Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs), or hybrid entropy generation techniques. Such mechanisms would preserve unpredictability even if the acoustic channel itself were partially influenced by an attacker.

The threat model considered in this work focuses on the injection of phantom objects through coordinated manipulation of camera and LiDAR [8] observations. The complementary problem of removing a legitimate object from the perception pipeline is not directly addressed by the current Conflict Detector design. Since the proposed detection logic relies on identifying unusual high-confidence detections, it is less suited to identifying the disappearance of previously tracked objects. Future work should investigate additional conflict-detection mechanisms based on object persistence, track continuity, and disappearance anomalies to provide symmetric protection against both object-injection and object-removal attacks.

The selection of frequency-agile FMCW radar [17] as the phantom sensing modality was motivated by current commercial availability. Dynamic wavelength LiDAR was considered as an alternative approach due to its ability to introduce similar unpredictability into the sensing process, but such systems remain largely experimental and are not yet widely available in

production automotive platforms. Should dynamically tunable LiDAR technologies become commercially viable, future work may explore multi-phantom architectures incorporating both radar and LiDAR as independently trusted sensing channels.

The radar-only navigation subsystem adopted during fallback operation is derived from prior radar navigation research. However, the studies forming the basis of this subsystem have been evaluated primarily in urban-driving and off-road environments [18] [19]. Their performance under sustained highway-speed conditions remains insufficiently explored. As a result, the operational envelope of the proposed fallback navigation strategy cannot yet be generalized to all driving conditions. Future work should evaluate radar-only fallback behavior across a broader range of traffic, weather, and speed scenarios to determine its practical limitations.

The current threat model assumes compromise of a majority, but not all, of the sensing modalities within the Main System. A more capable adversary able to manipulate camera, LiDAR, and the Main System radar (i.e. all the sensors) simultaneously would eliminate the confidence asymmetry exploited by Condition C within the Conflict Detector. While the Phantom System would continue to provide an independent cryptographically authenticated sensing channel, the effectiveness of the current conflict-detection logic under complete primary-sensor compromise has not been evaluated. Future work should investigate additional conflict conditions that do not depend on disagreement among conventional sensors and remain effective even when all primary sensing modalities are compromised.

The proposed architecture is primarily designed to address perception-layer attacks in which an adversary manipulates sensor observations to influence the autonomous driving decision process. It does not directly address physical tampering of sensors, wiring, or onboard hardware components. Prior work has explored tamper-resistant sensor architectures [9] intended to detect or resist physical interference with sensing hardware. Future work may investigate integrating such tamper-resistant mechanisms with the Phantom Channel Defense to provide protection against both perception-level manipulation and direct physical attacks. Combining independently trusted sensing channels with hardware tamper-resistance could provide a more comprehensive defense architecture spanning both cyber-physical and perception-layer threats.

Running the Main System and Phantom System concurrently during conflict operation introduces additional computational overhead that has not been formally characterized in this work. Although prior radar-only navigation research demonstrates real-time operation on physical platforms, the combined resource requirements of the proposed architecture remain unknown. Future work should evaluate CPU utilization, GPU utilization, memory consumption, and end-to-end latency during conflict operation to determine whether the architecture can operate within the constraints of production autonomous vehicle compute platforms.

Finally, this work presents a conceptual architecture intended for simulation-based evaluation. While simulation provides a controlled environment for studying attack and defense

behavior, it cannot fully capture real-world sensor imperfections, hardware timing variability, environmental noise, or operational safety constraints. Hardware-in-the-loop testing followed by structured on-road validation will be necessary before any claims regarding real-world deployment can be established. Consequently, implementation and empirical evaluation represent the most important next step for validating the practicality of the proposed architecture.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the Phantom Channel Defense, a security architecture designed to address coordinated cross-modal attacks against multi-sensor fusion perception systems in autonomous vehicles. The proposed approach introduces an isolated Phantom System that combines a cryptographically authenticated frequency-agile radar with radar-only fallback navigation, providing an independently trusted sensing channel outside the primary perception pipeline. By separating trust establishment from the compromised perception stack, the architecture seeks to maintain safe autonomous operation during sensor-conflict conditions without relying solely on emergency stops or immediate human intervention.

While the proposed design has not yet been implemented or experimentally validated, it establishes a framework for exploring resilient fallback mechanisms against increasingly sophisticated perception attacks. Future implementation, simulation-based evaluation, and real-world testing will be necessary to determine the effectiveness, performance overhead, and practical deployment considerations of the architecture. Nevertheless, the Phantom Channel Defense demonstrates how cryptographic trust mechanisms and independently verifiable sensing channels may be combined to strengthen the security and operational resilience of future autonomous vehicle systems.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. O.-R. A. V. S. Committee *et al.*, "Taxonomy and definitions for terms related to driving automation systems for on-road motor vehicles," *SAE International: Warrendale, PA, USA*, 2018.
- [2] Z. Liu, H. Tang, A. Amini, X. Yang, H. Mao, D. L. Rus, and S. Han, "Bevfusion: Multi-task multi-sensor fusion with unified bird's-eye view representation," in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2023, pp. 2774–2781.
- [3] R. Suzuki, T. Sato, Y. Hayakawa, K. Ikeda, O. Sako, R. Nagata, R. Yoshida, Q. A. Chen, and K. Yoshioka, "From lab to road: Realizing and detecting lidar spoofing attacks against autonomous vehicles at high speed and long distance," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 25, no. 13, pp. 25 661–25 681, 2025.
- [4] X. Hu, T. Liu, T. Shu, and D. Nguyen, "Spoofing detection for lidar in autonomous vehicles: A physical-layer approach," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 20 673–20 689, 2024.
- [5] B. Nassi, Y. Mirsky, D. Nassi, R. Ben-Netanel, O. Drokin, and Y. Elovici, "Phantom of the adas: Securing advanced driver-assistance systems from split-second phantom attacks," in *Proceedings of the 2020 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, ser. CCS '20. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2020, p. 293–308. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3372297.3423359>
- [6] F. Lin, H. Yan, J. Li, Z. Liu, L. Lu, Z. Ba, and K. Ren, "Phade: Practical phantom spoofing attack detection for autonomous vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, vol. 19, pp. 4199–4214, 2024.
- [7] J. Sun, Y. Cao, Q. A. Chen, and Z. M. Mao, "Towards robust LiDAR-based perception in autonomous driving: General black-box adversarial sensor attack and countermeasures," in *29th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 20)*. USENIX Association, Aug. 2020, pp. 877–894. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity20/presentation/sun>
- [8] S. Rahman Khan and R. Hasan, "Cross-Modal Phantom: Coordinated Camera-LiDAR Spoofing Against Multi-Sensor Fusion in Autonomous Vehicles," *arXiv e-prints*, p. arXiv:2604.21841, Apr. 2026.
- [9] J. Soryal, "Tamper-resistant sensor for autonomous vehicles," Sep. 27 2022, uS Patent 11,453,408.
- [10] C. Miller and C. Valasek, "Remote exploitation of an unaltered passenger vehicle," *Black Hat USA*, vol. 2015, no. S 91, pp. 1–91, 2015.
- [11] M. Turan, E. Barker, J. Kelsey, K. McKay, M. Baish, and M. Boyle, "Nist sp 800-90b recommendation for the entropy sources used for random bit generation. 2018."
- [12] H. Krawczyk and P. Eronen, "Hmac-based extract-and-expand key derivation function (hkdf)," *Tech. Rep.*, 2010.
- [13] E. B. Barker, E. B. Barker, D. Johnson, and M. E. Smid, *Recommendation for Pair-wise Key Establishment Schemes Using Discrete Logarithm Cryptography:(revised)*. US Department of Commerce, National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2007.
- [14] H. Krawczyk, M. Bellare, and R. Canetti, "Hmac: Keyed-hashing for message authentication," *Tech. Rep.*, 1997.
- [15] I. O. for Standardization, *ISO/SAE 21434: 2021: Road Vehicles: Cybersecurity Engineering*. ISO, 2021.
- [16] ISO, "Road vehicles — functional safety," International Organization for Standardization, *Tech. Rep. ISO 26262*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/68383.html>
- [17] C. Waldschmidt, J. Hasch, and W. Menzel, "Automotive radar—from first efforts to future systems," *IEEE Journal of Microwaves*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 135–148, 2021.
- [18] D. C. Herraes, M. Zeller, L. Chang, I. Vizzo, M. Heidingsfeld, and C. Stachniss, "Radar-only odometry and mapping for autonomous vehicles," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2024, pp. 10 275–10 282.
- [19] T. Overbye and S. Saripalli, "Radar-only off-road local navigation," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.17620>